

Introduction of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) as a Valuable Tool for Framing and Enhancing Forestry and Agriculture Development Policies

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Abstract: One of the main problems affecting the forestry and agriculture sectors in Croatia is the mismatch between cadastral records and the actual situation on the ground. Combined with unresolved ownership issues and negative demographic trends, this creates negative effects, including forest wildfires, loss of biodiversity and landscape diversity, reduced income from forestry and agriculture, and further depopulation of rural areas. In Croatia, 600,000–700,000 hectares of agricultural land are overgrown with forests (Ministry of Agriculture, 2021, p. 92). This paper proposes the Forest Regulation Index (FRI), defined as the ratio between actual forest cover and forests included in the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia. The index was calculated for regional and local self-government units using vector spatial data from Croatian Forests Ltd. together with high-resolution forest layers derived from publicly available Copernicus data. The resulting ratio can support agricultural and forestry development policies in a given area.

Keywords: managed forests; actual forest cover; regional self-government units; local self-government units; Copernicus high-resolution forest layers.

1 Introduction

Natural succession on abandoned agricultural land is a major challenge in Croatia and Southeast Europe, largely driven by rural depopulation. The literature repeatedly highlights fragmented land ownership, small forest holdings, and rural decline. Much of Croatia's forest area has developed on former cultivated land still recorded as agricultural in cadastral records, creating difficulties for management planning (Paladinić 2018). In addition, there is no unique, comprehensive registry of agricultural land, forms of use and management (Vidaček 2019).

Forest ownership in Croatia is highly fragmented. Most private owners possess less than 20 ha, and the average holding is well below one hectare. This hinders sustainable management and often leads to economically inefficient use of resources. Unresolved property relations and inconsistencies between cadastral and land-register data further reduce management in private forests to uncoordinated individual operations, complicating planning at broader spatial scales (Editorial Board 2020).

These problems are critical for the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia, understood here as forests covered by official forest management plans. The literature points to fragmentation, inactive owners, irregular management, and insufficient financial and institutional

support. Small forest holdings, typically under 1 ha, are a major limiting factor for effective management (Božić et al. 2022).

Succession of woody vegetation on former agricultural land creates problems ranging from biodiversity and landscape diversity loss to increased fire risk. Reliable information on the extent of this process is therefore essential for development policies and strategic documents, including the National Forestry Strategy and the Forest Management Plan for the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia. This paper therefore proposes the Forest Regulation Index (FRI), defined as the ratio between forest areas under official management plans and actual forest cover.

Although the problem is well recognized, Croatia still lacks a systematic and comparable approach to assessing forest succession on abandoned agricultural land. The issue appears only sporadically in planning and environmental documents, and there is no database allowing comparison across space or time. It is also often omitted because it largely concerns private parcels. The FRI is therefore proposed as a simple complementary indicator of the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning. It is presented here as an initial methodological step rather than a finished product and requires further refinement, testing, and validation. The objective of this study is to introduce the FRI as a simple and comparable indicator of the relationship between actual forest cover and forests included in the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia.

2 Materials and methods

Two datasets were used: forests included in active official management plans and actual forest cover derived from recent spatial sources. The first was obtained from the Web Feature Service (WFS) of Croatian Forests Ltd. for state-owned and private forests, the second from Copernicus high-resolution forest layers based on Sentinel-2 imagery. Comparing these datasets enables calculation of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI), the ratio between managed forest areas and actual forest cover, at the national, county, and municipal levels.

To ensure comparability, both input datasets were refined before calculating the FRI. In this study, “managed forests” refer only to forest areas covered by official management plans and classified as covered forest land, while “actual forest cover” refers to the Copernicus 2021 high-resolution forest layer after refinement according to the legal

minimum area threshold and masking of actively managed agricultural land recorded in ARKOD.

For the purposes of data refinement, the legal definition of forest was aligned with the Croatian Forest Act, which defines forest as follows:

“Forest is defined as land continuously covered by forest trees and/or their shrubby forms over an area of 0.1 ha or larger, where forest products are permanently produced and ecosystem services are provided.”

Given the 10 m resolution of the HRL layer, raster data were refined to exclude areas with fewer than 10 connected pixels (1,000 m²). This removes individual trees, hedgerows, and tree lines not legally considered forests. Refinement was performed in QGIS using a sieve algorithm with 8-connectedness.

The HRL layer was further refined using the ARKOD database to identify actively managed agricultural land. Orchards, olive groves, and vineyards may appear as forest in the HRL layer because of their spectral characteristics, so ARKOD was used to distinguish active perennial crops from abandoned land undergoing succession. Because ARKOD registration is voluntary, some unregistered plantations may still introduce minor bias.

The official management dataset was filtered to include only covered forest land. Non-covered productive and non-productive land, non-fertile land, and degraded Mediterranean shrub forms such as maquis and garrigue were excluded to ensure comparability with actual forest cover.

Forests of special purpose, including national parks, strict reserves, and large military training areas, were excluded because their documentation is not uniformly available and these areas are not subject to regular commercial management. Military-area polygons were obtained from OpenStreetMap.

After refinement, the calculation (equation 1) of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) represents the ratio between the area covered by forest management plans and the actual forest-covered area:

$$FRI = \frac{\text{Area covered by forest management plans}}{\text{Actual forest-covered area (HRL dataset)}} \quad (1)$$

The resulting FRI value can be expressed at different spatial levels, providing a valuable tool for regional and local policymakers.

FRI is a dimensionless ratio with a theoretical range from 0 to 1. Values closer to 1 indicate a higher degree of correspondence between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning, while lower values indicate a greater mismatch between these two categories.

For map display, FRI values were classified separately for county and local levels using the Jenks natural breaks

method. Because the distributions of values differ between these spatial levels, the resulting classes are interpretative and not universal thresholds.

The analysis combines datasets of different origin, structure, and spatial resolution, introducing uncertainty. The official management dataset is based on vector administrative records, while actual forest cover is derived from 10 m remote sensing data. Minor boundary mismatches and omission/commission errors may therefore occur, especially in fragmented landscapes and transitional vegetation forms. The refinement steps improve comparability but do not eliminate all spatial and classification uncertainty.

3 Results

This research proposes the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) at the regional and local self-government levels. Since the index refers to coverage by forest management plans, the term “regulation” was considered more appropriate than “management”, which implies a broader scope of activities. The regional FRI is shown in Figure 1 and the local FRI in Figure 2. Local-level symbology was recalibrated to account for greater variance, and a “not available” category was introduced for local self-government units Jarmina and Opuzen, where the absence of designated forest management areas precluded index computation. In areas with negligible forest cover, the interpretive usefulness of the index is limited.

To maintain conciseness, detailed tables were omitted and average values were prioritized. The national FRI stands at 0.78, while the regional and local averages are 0.77 and 0.72, respectively (Table 1). Although the cumulative forest area remains constant, these variations across administrative tiers result from the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP).

This difference reflects MAUP, i.e. the fact that aggregated indicator values change with the spatial scale and administrative partition used in the analysis. At the local level, smaller and more heterogeneous units generate a wider spread of FRI values, affecting both averages and class structure. The difference between national, county, and local averages should therefore be interpreted as a scale effect inherent to spatial aggregation.

Overall, the results show that the FRI is spatially uneven. Higher values are concentrated in areas with stronger continuity of forest management, while lower values point to areas where forest succession has expanded beyond the scope of formally managed forests. The maps therefore help identify spatial patterns directly relevant to the study objective.

The differences between county- and local-level classes result from the different distributions of FRI values at these spatial levels. For this reason, Jenks natural breaks

Table 1. Mean, minimum and maximum FRI at state, county and local level.

Spatial level	Number of units	Mean FRI	Minimum	Maximum
National	1	0.78	0.78	0.78
County	21	0.77	0.59	0.89
Local self-government units	555	0.72	0.00	0.95

classification was applied separately to each level in order to identify interpretable class boundaries. These classes were used for cartographic presentation and should not be understood as fixed universal thresholds.

Figure 1. Forest Regulation Index (FRI) at regional (county) level.

Figure 2. Forest Regulation Index (FRI) at local (towns and municipalities) level.

4 Discussion

The results show that the highest FRI values are concentrated in Eastern Slavonia and in Lika-Senj County, where forestry has strong historical importance. Conversely, Gorski Kotar yielded lower-than-anticipated values. Counties severely affected by war and subsequent depopulation, such as Karlovac, Sisak-Moslavina, and Brod-Posavina, show lower forest regulation.

A notable anomaly is Istria County, where a low FRI contrasts with a high regional development index. This may reflect high rates of private land ownership and a lack of systematic management. In coastal regions, the FRI decreases from west to east, reaching its minimum in Dubrovnik-Neretva County. This pattern is consistent with the economic shift from the primary sector to tourism, former agricultural and forest-dependent livelihoods have largely been replaced by more lucrative tourism-related activities.

At the local level, high FRI values align with major forest massifs in Slavonia, Gorski Kotar, and Lika. Istria remains ambivalent, with higher indices in the mountainous eastern areas and lower values in the central peninsula. The low index in Međimurje County, despite its high development status, underscores that the FRI, linked to the primary economic sector, does not inherently correlate with overall economic prosperity. However, in units devastated by war and long-term depopulation, a possible association can be observed between low forest regulation and poor development indicators.

These spatial patterns are consistent with earlier literature emphasizing the effects of agricultural land abandonment, cadastral mismatch, fragmented ownership, and weak management continuity in private forests (Paladinić 2018, Vidaček 2019, Editorial Board 2020, Božić et al. 2022). In this sense, the FRI does not replace existing knowledge but provides a spatially comparable way of expressing patterns already recognized in qualitative and sectoral analyses.

The FRI is not intended to directly predict fire risk, productivity, or biodiversity outcomes, but rather to serve as an initial spatial indicator of the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning.

5 Conclusions

The abandonment of rural areas and resulting natural forest succession represent major challenges for Croatia's forestry and agriculture. This trend is tied to rural depopulation and is associated with biodiversity loss, reduced landscape diversity, and increased forest fire risk.

The Forest Regulation Index (FRI) can support policymakers, particularly in updating forestry policy and preparing strategic environmental assessments. By indicating the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning, it helps identify areas where agricultural land is being lost to forest overgrowth and where targeted policy measures may be justified.

The scientific contribution of this study lies in proposing the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) as a simple and spatially comparable indicator of the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning. At the same time, the study should be understood as an initial methodological step, since the index remains sensitive to data quality, spatial scale, and the limits of comparability between different datasets. Future research should therefore focus on further refinement and validation of the FRI, while its present form

may already support the identification of priority areas for forestry and agricultural policy measures.

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